

PREDICTION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

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1. Introduction

In the literature, static and fatigue failure criteria for unidirectional (UD) composites are mostly based on macromechanical quantities as the nominal stresses in the material coordinate system, which are often involved in a polynomial expression describing the failure condition. Tsai-Hill and Tsai-Wu criteria are classical examples for the static behaviour. An improvement to them is achieved by Puck's polynomial criterion [1], since it involves the macroscopic stresses lying on the fracture plane. However it is always a macroscopic criterion, based on phenomenological expressions which do not account for the actual damage mechanisms at the microscopic scale. Concerning the fatigue behaviour, some empirical criteria are available in the literature, providing sometimes not accurate predictions, as discussed in [2]. In addition, Kawai [3] extended the Tsai-Hill polynomial criterion to fatigue, combining it with a continuum damage model, but without taking into account the different damage mechanisms responsible for the fatigue failure. Moreover, the fact of describing with one only equation the fatigue behaviour for both fibre and matrix-dominated response seems not to have a physical meaning, according to the authors' opinion. Before Kawai, Hashin and Rotem [4] proposed a polynomial criterion, separating the fibre and the matrix dominated behaviours, which have to be described with different expressions, whose application depends on which is the critical component in the composite lamina (fibre or matrix). In particular, for the matrix dominated behaviour they proposed a polynomial expression involving the transverse and in plane shear stresses, weighted by means of fatigue functions to be experimentally calibrated. Therefore, in

spite of the merit of treating separately the fibre and matrix dominated behaviours, this criterion still considers the macroscopic nominal stresses, involved in a phenomenological expression. Concerning the non-fibre dominated behaviour, some efforts in the direction of considering the local stresses (or micro-stresses) acting in the matrix have been presented by Reifsneider and Gao in 1991 [5]. They used the Mori-Tanaka theory in order to evaluate the average transverse stress and in-plane shear stress in the matrix, and involved them in a criterion similar to that of Hashin, using some fatigue function of empirical derivation. In spite of the use of the local average stresses, this is still a phenomenological criterion, and it requires a large experimental effort for the model calibration. In 1999 Plumtree and Cheng [6] developed a model based on the local stresses acting on the fracture plane, defined as the plane normal to the transverse direction. According to this choice for the fracture plane, the relevant stresses turned out to be the local transverse and in plane shear stresses only, calculated by means of Finite Element (FE) analyses of a fibre-matrix unit cell. In addition they took inspiration from the Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) criterion for metals [7] to account for the presence of a non zero mean stress.

The aim of the present work is to define a physically based criterion, suitable to describe the non-fibre dominated fatigue behaviour, in terms of crack initiation, of UD laminae subjected to multiaxial loading, characterized by the presence of the in-plane stress components σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 (see figure 1 for the definition of stresses).

The proposed model is based on the damage modes experimentally observed by the present authors [8] and from the literature, as will be better explained in the next section. Its application

to a large bulk of experimental data reveals a good accuracy.

Fig. 1: Global and material coordinate system, and stresses in the material coordinate system

2. Mechanisms of fatigue failure

First of all, some preliminary considerations about the peculiarities of fatigue failure are needed. If an UD lamina is subjected to a cyclic loading condition leading to a matrix-dominated response, it fails without a visible progressive damage [8-10]. This means that a stable crack propagation is not observed and, conversely, when a macro-crack (visible crack) nucleates, it propagates unstably bringing the lamina to the complete fracture in just few cycles.

Therefore, from many experimental evidences, it can be concluded that the matrix-dominated fatigue failure is controlled by the initiation phase, if the word “*initiation*” is referred to a macro-crack parallel to the fibres. However, at a microscopic level, a sort of degradation process has to take place during fatigue life, otherwise the decreasing trend of the fatigue S-N curves cannot be explained [11]. As a consequence, a driving force for the micro-damage progression leading to the final macro-crack onset has to be established, and it cannot be done regardless of the damage modes at the microscopic scale, responsible for the macro-crack initiation. In order to do that, the concept of the fracture plane is introduced in the following. As already mentioned, Puck’s criterion is based on the fact that the effective stresses to be considered as the cause of the static failure are the stresses lying on the fracture plane.

According to Puck, in the case of positive values of σ_2 and σ_6 , the fracture plane is always the plane whose normal is the transverse direction, and therefore the effective stresses are simply the global stress components σ_2 and σ_6 . The importance of the fracture plane is emphasized also by Plumtree and Cheng [6], and also for them, in the case of an off-axis lamina, the stress components to be accounted for are σ_2 and σ_6 only, because they act on the plane normal to the 2-direction.

macroscopic fracture plane

Fig. 2: macroscopic and local fracture plane

The main merit of their criterion is that it considers the peak local stresses in the matrix, resulting from the concentrations due the presence of the fibres, instead of the global stresses.

It is important to underline that the fracture plane considered by Puck and by Plumtree-Cheng is actually a final separation plane, it can be referred to as a *macroscopic fracture plane*. The actual fracture plane, in which the matrix micro-cracking and the degradation process occurs, is not parallel to the fibres, and this is confirmed by experimental observations of the fracture surfaces that can be found in [8, 9]. In figure 2 the concept of the *local fracture plane* is introduced, as the plane in which the micro-damage occurs by means of matrix micro-cracks.

Therefore a criterion to assess the local fracture plane is required. In the present work, according to the experimental evidences, it is considered as the plane perpendicular to the local maximum principal stress. As a consequence, the effective stress to be considered is the Local Maximum Principal Stress (LMPS) in the matrix, which has to be calculated by considering the local stress fields, i.e. the micro-stresses.

In addition, Asp et al.[12, 13] in 1996 proved that, since the local stress state at or close to the fibre-matrix interface is nearly hydrostatic, in the case of pure transverse tension, the static failure is caused by the resin cavitation. Therefore a good criterion for predicting the composite failure in the case of pure transverse stress is based on reaching a critical value for the dilatational energy density expressed as

$$U_v = \frac{1-2\nu}{6E} I_1^2 \quad (1)$$

where I_1 is the first stress tensor invariant, which has to be calculated considering the local stress fields. In [13] good agreement was found between predictions based on this criterion and experimental results for the transverse static strength of a UD lamina.

Therefore it is reasonable to expect a change in the leading damage mode moving from a loading condition near the pure transverse stress to another one, characterized by the presence of an enough high shear stress component. According to this idea the following criterion for multiaxial fatigue is proposed: the parameters representative of the driving forces for the two main damage mechanisms have to be used, according to the multiaxial condition, namely:

- the peak value of the Local Hydrostatic Stress $LHS = I_1/3$, for nearly pure transverse tension case;
- the peak value of the Local Maximum Principal Stress (LMPS) for the other conditions, when the shear stress component is high enough.

3. Calculation of the local stresses

As stated above, the driving force for the microscopic damage evolution has to be expressed in terms of local stresses (or micro-stresses) acting in the matrix and at the fibre-matrix interface. In the present work a regular square fibres array is assumed for the calculation of the micro-stresses. Of course it is not exactly representative of the real composite system, because of the non uniform actual fibres distribution, but it has been shown to provide reliable results in terms of stress concentrations, if compared to a random fibre array [14]. However, a reasonable simplification of the problem under analysis has to be accepted for the definition of a criterion of practical use and industrial appeal. Because of the geometrical symmetry only one quarter of a unit cell can be considered for the calculation, as shown in figure 3.

The local stresses have been calculated by means of FE analyses of a fibre-matrix unit cell subjected to the average, or macroscopic stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 . Periodic boundary conditions have been applied to the surfaces of the quarter of the unit cell as shown in [15]. In addition, also the residual stresses due to the cooling process after curing should be considered, and the thermal load has been applied as a uniform temperature jump $\Delta T = T_c - T_r$, where T_c is the curing temperature and T_r is the room temperature.

Fig. 3: definition of the fibre-matrix unit cell for micromechanical analysis

Since the fatigue loads are lower than the static failure loads, the matrix behaviour is considered mostly linear, and therefore linear elastic analyses have been conducted with the software ANSYS 11[®] using 20 nodes solid elements.

At each point P of the unit cell the mechanical micro-stresses in polar coordinates (r, θ, z) can be expressed in terms of stress concentration factors $k_{i,jl}$ relating the nominal external stress σ_i with the local stress σ_{jl} , as in equation (2). Finally the thermal stresses are related to the temperature jump ΔT by means of thermal concentration factors h_{jl} , as in equation (2).

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{rr} \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{r\theta} \\ \sigma_{\theta z} \\ \sigma_{rz} \end{Bmatrix}^P = \begin{bmatrix} k_{1,rr} & k_{2,rr} & k_{6,rr} \\ k_{1,\theta\theta} & k_{2,\theta\theta} & k_{6,\theta\theta} \\ k_{1,zz} & k_{2,zz} & k_{6,zz} \\ k_{1,r\theta} & k_{2,r\theta} & k_{6,r\theta} \\ k_{1,\theta z} & k_{2,\theta z} & k_{6,\theta z} \\ k_{1,rz} & k_{2,rz} & k_{6,rz} \end{bmatrix}^P \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{Bmatrix} + \Delta T \begin{Bmatrix} h_{rr} \\ h_{\theta\theta} \\ h_{zz} \\ h_{r\theta} \\ h_{\theta z} \\ h_{rz} \end{Bmatrix}^P \quad (2)$$

The stress concentration factors are functions of the fibre volume fraction V_f and the elastic properties of the fibre/matrix system. In the case of glass/epoxy composites, typical values for the Young moduli E and Poisson's ratio ν have been used in the subsequent analyses, and they are listed in table 1. The adopted Coefficients of Thermal Expansion (CTE) for the constituents are also listed in table 1.

	E (MPa)	ν	CTE ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)
Glass	70000	0.22	$7 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Epoxy	3200	0.37	$67.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Table 1: Typical glass/epoxy material properties used in the FE analyses

The peak values of the local LMPS and LHS have been found to be always between the points A or B (mostly at point A) of figure 3 where, because of symmetry, some stress components vanish leading to the following simple expressions for LMPS and LHS:

$$MPS = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{zz} + \sqrt{\sigma_{rr}^2 + 4\sigma_{rz}^2 - 2\sigma_{rr}\sigma_{zz} + \sigma_{zz}^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$LHS = \frac{\sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{\theta\theta} + \sigma_{zz}}{3} \quad (4)$$

where the stresses defined by equation (2) have to be substituted. According to the criterion proposed at the end of section 2, the LMPS defined in equation (3) has to be used as fatigue parameter in order to present fatigue S-N data for general multiaxial conditions, not nearly in pure transverse tension. Conversely, in such a condition the parameter LHS defined in equation (4) has to be used as representative of the driving force for damage evolution. In the following section the fatigue results from different literature works are reanalyzed in terms of LMPS and LHS.

4. Application to experimental data

4.1 Fatigue results on tubular specimens

In [8] the authors presented the experimental results on glass/epoxy (G/E) pipes with the fibres oriented at 90° with respect to the axis of the tube, and subjected to combined tension-torsion cyclic loading, resulting in the stress components σ_2 and σ_6 . A load ratio $R = 0.05$ was adopted. A parameter $\lambda_{12} = \sigma_6/\sigma_2$ was defined [2] in order to describe the biaxiality condition. In [8] fatigue curves were presented for $\lambda_{12} = 0, 1$ and 2 , and here some additional data are presented, for $\lambda_{12} =$

3 and ∞ (pure torsion). In figure 4a) the S-N curves are shown in terms of the maximum cyclic value of the transverse stress $\sigma_{2,max}$, showing a significant influence of the biaxiality ratio on the fatigue resistance.

Fig. 4: fatigue results for tubes: maximum a) cyclic transverse stress and b) LMPS against the number of cycles to failure N_f

Fig. 5: fatigue results on flat [4]: maximum a) cyclic global stress and b) LMPS against the number of cycles to failure N_f

In figure 4b) the fatigue data are plotted in terms of the maximum cyclic value of the LMPS, calculated by means of the micromechanical analysis described in section 3. It can be seen that the curves for $\lambda_{12} \geq 1$ are reasonably well collapsed into a narrow scatter band, indicating that, in these conditions, the LMPS is representative of the driving force for the damage evolution bringing the lamina to the fatigue failure. Conversely, lower values of LMPS are found for the curve corresponding to $\lambda_{12} = 0$ (pure transverse stress). This is not surprising, since the hydrostatic component of the stress tensor becomes dominant in such a condition, becoming the leading driving force for the damage evolution, as reported in section 2. In fact, if all the curves are plotted in terms of the local value of LHS, the pure tension curve would be higher than the others. The figure is not shown for a matter of space, but the distribution of fatigue data is similar to that observed in figure 4a), being LHS dependent on σ_2 and on the residual stresses only.

4.2 Fatigue results on flat specimens from Hashin and Rotem [4]

Hashin and Rotem [4] presented the results of fatigue tests on flat UD G/E laminae subjected to off-axis loading with $R = 0.1$, resulting in a multiaxial state with the presence of all the three in-plane stress components. In figure 5a) the results are shown in terms of the maximum cyclic value of the global applied stress in the loading direction $\sigma_{x,max}$. Different fatigue curves are related to different off-axis angles, if plotted in terms of the global stress, but they are well collapsed into a single scatter band when LMPS is used to present fatigue data, as can be seen in figure 5b).

In this case all the curves, for off-axis angles from 5 to 60 degrees, are well described by the LMPS, which turns out to be once again a suitable parameter to represent the driving force for fatigue damage in loading conditions far from the pure transverse stress.

4.3 Fatigue results on flat specimens from El Kadi and Ellyin [10]

In [10] El-Kadi and Ellyin tested flat unidirectional G/E specimens subjected to cyclic off-axis loading with three values of the load ratio $R (-1, 0, 0.5)$. In the following only the results for

$R = 0$ are shown for a matter of space, but the case of $R = 0.5$ leads to very similar conclusions.

Due to a change in the damage mechanism the model cannot be directly applied for tension-compression loading.

Figure 6 shows that different fatigue curves are obtained if the results are expressed in terms of the maximum applied stress in the loading direction.

Fig. 6: fatigue results on flat [10]: maximum cyclic global stress against the number of cycles to failure N_f

In figure 7a) the results are reanalyzed in terms of LMPS, where it can be noticed that the curves for off-axis angles of 19 and 45 degrees can be reasonably thought to be collapsed into a single scatter band, while the other curves clearly exhibit lower values of LMPS. In fact these curves are related to loading conditions characterized by a highly hydrostatical local stress state and they exhibit higher values of LHS, as can be seen in figure 7b). The curve for 45° seems to be included in both the scatter bands, in terms of LMPS and LHS, and this is probably because it is representative of a stress state close to the transition zone from one leading damage mode to the other.

5. Damage evolution in multidirectional laminates

In paragraph 4 it has been shown that only two scatter bands, in terms of LHS and LMPS, are suitable to describe the multiaxial fatigue behaviour of UD laminae, when the shear stress component is very low or high enough respectively, compared to the transverse stress. The so obtained master curves and scatter bands can therefore be used to predict the fatigue life of a unidirectional lamina in multiaxial conditions. It is once again reminded

that the present model can be used only for the prediction of a macro-crack initiation, which, in the case of a UD lamina, corresponds to the final failure since it is not subjected to a stable propagation or crack multiplication process.

Fig. 7: fatigue results on flat [10]: maximum a) LMPS and b) LHS against the number of cycles to failure N_f

In most of practical applications, multidirectional laminates made of UD laminae are used, and their fatigue life is characterized by the nucleation of multiple cracks in the off-axis plies [16].

This kind of damage is usually described in terms of crack density evolution during fatigue life, whose effect is the degradation of the global elastic properties of the laminate. For this reason it is important to be able to predict the crack density evolution during the fatigue life of a multidirectional laminate. To this aim a semi-analytical procedure is being developed by the present authors. It is based on the idea that the initiation of cracks in the off-axis plies is controlled by the matrix-dominated fatigue behaviour of the single UD lamina, which has been shown to be successfully described by representing the S-N curves in terms of LHS and LMPS parameters. Being them local quantities, a multiscale analysis is required, involving the

following steps, briefly summarised in the following.

- 1) Calculation of ply stresses in each layer, with the possible presence of off-axis cracks, and therefore considering the stress redistribution between them and between layers;
- 2) Calculation of micro-stresses (or local stresses) by means of a fibre-matrix unit cell subjected to periodic boundary conditions;
- 3) Calculation of the fatigue parameters LHS and LMPS;
- 4) According to the multiaxiality condition, calculation of the life spent for the nucleation of a new crack, by using the LHS or LMPS master curves for the material considered;
- 5) Coming back to point 1).

In the application of step 4) many aspects of fundamental importance have to be considered, as the statistical distribution of fatigue strength, the constraining effect due to the presence of other plies and sequence effect due to the fact that, because of load redistribution after cracking, the local cycles amplitude continuously changes during fatigue life.

For a more detailed description of the procedure and its validation, we refer the reader to a work which is being published by the authors [17].

6. Discussion and conclusions

A criterion for the description of the non-fibre dominated fatigue behaviour of UD laminae has been proposed, suitable to deal with multiaxial conditions. The aim of the work was to identify the parameters representative of the driving force for the damage evolution during fatigue life. According to experimental observations [8], the concept of the *local fracture plane* has been introduced and it has been identified as the plane normal to the Local Maximum Principal Stress (LMPS) calculated by means of micromechanical analyses. The LMPS parameter has been found to collapse in one single scatter band the fatigue curves related to multiaxial loading conditions, not in nearly pure transverse stress. In fact in such conditions the local stress state in the matrix is highly hydrostatical, and it is reasonable to assume that this produces a change in the leading damage mode. In this work the local value of the hydrostatic stress LHS has been shown to be a suitable parameter to collect fatigue data in the case of loading conditions with a low shear stress,

compared to the transverse stress. Therefore only two scatter bands, and related master curves, can be used for multiaxial fatigue design of composite laminae, depending on the multiaxial stress state. The condition corresponding to the transition between the two leading damage modes is a property of the composite system.

The proposed criterion can be used as a basis for the development of a semi-analytical procedure for the prediction of the crack density evolution in multidirectional laminates under fatigue loading.

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